

Newton's First and Second Laws Leading to Different Spatial Probabilities One Being Quantum Mechanical?

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Newton's second $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ where p is momentum is equivalent to $pp/2m + V(x) = E$ for a conservative force $= -dV/dx$ with $p = m_0 v(x)$, v being velocity. In general one may divide the x axis into equally spaced dx units with $dt(x)$ (i.e. time spent) differing in each unit. A main point we wish to make is that $dt(x)$ is the same whether the particle moves to the right or to left. Thus using $dt(x)$ as a kind of density (proportional to $C/v(x)$) as done in (1) means this spatial density does not distinguish between motion to the right or left. This is one kind of spatial density we argue, one that considers only the magnitude of velocity. Heuristically, however, one might argue that motion to the right or left involves a skewed spatial density in the direction of motion. This we argue represents a second kind of spatial density which follows from Newton's first law and is associated with quantum mechanical motion. Ideally the two should be linked.

Newton's first law indicates that a particle at rest remains at rest and one in constant motion in a direction continues in this state unless acted on by force. This law is usually not associated with a mathematical equation and so a spatial density is not derived. In (2), however, we argue that Newton's first law is associated with invariance in a spatial direction if there is no force in that direction, for example x . In such a case, d/dx is the translation generator in that direction and momentum is kind of "information". We argued in (2) that one may write $d/dx f(x) = p$ to describe this with the simplest solution being $f(x) = px$ for constant p . We further argued that this is in fact linked to Fermat's least time principle for light. Time = distance/speed of light, but momentum and displacement are parallel. Thus for a two dimensional problem: $p \cdot r = (p_x)x + (p_y)y = p \text{ distance} = p \sqrt{xx+YY}$ and $p \sqrt{(L-x)(L-x) + YY}$ for two rays, one being the incident and the other the reflected. Given that there is conservation of momentum in the x direction one may write $(p_x) \text{ incident} = (p_x) \text{ reflected}$ or $d/dx (p \text{ distance incident}) - d/dx (p \text{ distance reflected}) = 0$ which is Fermat's principle for reflection with one index of refraction. For refraction $p_1 = p n_1$ and $p_2 = p n_2$, but $(p_1)_x = (p_2)_x$.

$f(x) = px$ satisfies $d/dx f(x) = p$. This expression depends on x , but also on the direction of motion i.e. one may have p or $-p$. In (2) we further argued that this expression may be written in terms of: $i px = \ln(\exp(ipx))$ with $\exp(ipx)$ being periodic, but neither growing or tending to a constant zero for a constant p . As a result we identified $\exp(ipx)$ with a second type of spatial density or probability, one which accounts for the direction of motion. $\exp(ipx)$ is also associated with a quantum mechanical description of a free particle. Thus Newton's first two laws give rise to two different spatial densities, but they are related. In particular, the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ equals constant which is $P(x)$ or spatial density from Newton's second law.

In this note, we start with the assumption that a velocity (not velocity magnitude) spatial density should exist and examine what properties of such a density/probability arise.

Newton's Second Law and Spatial Density

Newton's second law written in the form $p^2/2m + V(x) = E$ focuses on energy and not on the direction of motion in the sense that p and $-p$ at x have the same energy. Thus if one divides the x axis into equally spaced units dx , $t(x)$ becomes the important piece of information for each dx and $dt(x)$ does not depend on the direction of motion. Thus one may create a kind of density equal to $dt(x) = C/|v(x)|$ where $v(x)$ is speed as done in (1). If one considers Newton's second law $dp/dt = \text{Force}$, p is linear and so it may appear that direction is considered, but $d/dt \rightarrow v(x) d/dx$ so $dp/dt = v(x) d/dx p(x)$ which is quadratic in $v(x)$.

Newton's First Law and Spatial Density

We argue that Newton's second law leads to a spatial density which is dependent on the direction of motion/momentum unlike the case with the second law. We use spatial invariance (and d/dx the generator of translations in such an invariant direction) to establish this relationship noting that; $d/dx f(x) = p$ has $f(x) = px$ as a solution. " Px " is essentially time used in Fermat's least time principle applied to reflection from a stationary mirror with one index of refraction. The point we make is that $d/dx f(x) = p$ depends on the direction of p . If one wishes to convert this into the form of a probability/spatial density, we argued in (2) that one may write: $-id/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = px$. Then $\exp(ipx)$ represents an unusual momentum direction related density which has wavelengths which should be physical. This density is linked to that from Newton's second law by taking the modulus. It should be linked because the periodicity comes from distinguishing the direction of motion. If one ignores such a distinction as in the case of energy considerations then all x points become the same and density should be constant not periodic for constant motion. Thus one must be able to map $\exp(ipx)$ into a constant at each x . We note that $\exp(ipx)$ is the form of probability for a quantum mechanical free particle.

Constant Velocity/Momentum Not Speed Dependent Spatial Density

We now try to consider properties of a constant velocity (not velocity magnitude) related density a priori without using d/dx the generator of translations. (We, however, use p momentum instead of v .)

First we argue that motion to the right and left are different and we seek a spatial density/probability which distinguishes the two as $P(x) = C/|v(x)|$ does not. We expect that motion to the right should have a density skewed to the right and motion to the left, one skewed to the left. If one thinks of spatial density as being linked to probability, one might expect:

$$P(p, x) + P(-p, x) = \text{function which does not distinguish the direction of } p = \text{function even in } p \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{Thus we postulate: } P(p, x) = F(\text{odd})(p, x) + G(\text{even})(p, x) \quad ((2))$$

Furthermore we require that $P(p, x)$ have a semblance of being the same for all x . $P(p, x)$ cannot be a constant because this does not distinguish between forward and negative motion. The next

best choice is periodic motion, but this may still involve a strictly positive function. This suggests that at least $F(\text{odd})(p,x)$ be periodic.

The notion of a periodic function immediately involves a number of issues/ideas:

((A)) Different p values should have different “wavelengths” in order to be distinguishable in terms of spatial probability. This would have to be experimentally verifiable.

((B)) The wavelengths may have major importance if a particle is confined to a fixed length region of the order of magnitude of wavelength. In such a case one may argue that a periodic hump identifies p and so a full hump should fit into L . This suggests that there is zero point motion because the largest hump to fit into L would represent a ground state. Furthermore only integer numbers of humps may fit into L so there is discretization of energy.

((C)) There seems to be an issue or problem because a periodic density means that there are x regions with almost no probability while constant motion (momentum) implies that all x points should be treated equally as $C/|v(x)|$ with $|v(x)| = \text{constant}$ ensures.

We consider the problem ((C)). In the above discussion we focus on a probability/spatial density which captures the direction of motion/momentum as well as its magnitude for constant motion. This is linked with the idea of momentum which is a vector. There is, however, also energy which is a scalar and does not distinguish between the direction of motion, but depends only on magnitude. This is the probability or density which follows from Newton’s second law. Is there any way to make a velocity dependent probability consistent with one which does not distinguish direction of motion? The idea of a periodic spatial probability appeared only because one required that the direction of constant motion be distinguished. If one does not need to distinguish then all x points should have the same weight. Such a picture is linked with energy as information. In such a case, different energy states (different constant momentum magnitudes) should be physically distinguishable with x removed from the picture. To remove x , one usually integrates over x .

For a free particle $E = p^2/2m$. This implies $p = +a$ or $p = -a$. From the above, however, we see that adding $P(p,x)$ and $P(-p,x)$ leads to periodicity, not a constant in space. If one seeks a constant probability density and both $P(p,x)$ and $P(-p,x)$ are periodic, one would argue combining these in an “equal footing manner” to create a constant. This suggests a consideration of:

$$P(p,x)P(-p,x) = \text{constant} \quad ((3))$$

If this is the case, however, what does $P(p_1,x)P(p_2,x)$ or its integral over x imply? Given that p_1 and p_2 have different identities one would expect:

$$\text{Integral } P(p_1,x)P(p_2,x) dx = 0 \text{ for } 1 \text{ not equal to } 2 \quad ((4))$$

((3)) and ((4)) are forms from linear algebra. In particular, ((4)) is a dot product and ((3)) is a term in a dot product. In ((4)) one must have $P(p,x)$ take on both positive and negative values. Thus the periodicity in ((2)) involves both positive and negative values. A real periodic function multiplied by itself cannot yield a constant for ((3)) thus this seems to suggest that ((2)) be a vector in at least two dimensions.

A solution to the above conditions is $P(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$ which follows almost immediately from ((3)) and guarantees ((4)). For example, for ((3)) to hold a^p is a solution, but this grows or decreases so one replaces p so one may use $\exp(ipx)$ which is periodic and of the same form.

As a result, we argue that both Newton's first law and independent considerations of a spatial density/probability which recognizes direction of motion both lead to the "probability" $\exp(ipx)$ for constant motion. This is linked to the probability from Newton's second law by taking the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$. In general, one may create more complicated densities by taking a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s i.e. $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ such that $W^*(x)W(x)$ would be the density from Newton's second law.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that Newton's first and second laws lead to different, yet linked, spatial densities/probabilities. Newton's second law is equivalent to $pp/2m + V(x) = E$ and so does not distinguish between forward and backwards motion with the same magnitude of p as these have the same energy. Thus $dt(x)$, the time spent in equally spaced dx units governs the density (1). Heuristically, however, this is bothersome because motion to the right and left should be distinguishable spatially i.e. through some kind of spatial probability.

Newton's first law, which is usually given in words and not formula, however, leads to such a density as one may use spatial invariance to define: $d/dx f(x) = p$ where p demonstrates direction in space. A solution is $f(x) = px$, but this cannot be a density because it grows. One may use, however, $-i d/dx \ln(\exp(ipx)) = p$ where $\exp(ipx)$ may be considered a kind of spatial density/probability which differs for p and $-p$. This density is not independent of the one from the second law as the modulus of $\exp(ipx)$ yields a constant which is the result from Newton's second law.

In this note we try to show that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ without directly using the d/dx operator, but this involves the notion of considering products of a velocity (direction) dependent probability and integrating to either obtain a constant or 0. Thus the idea of orthogonality of energy states emerges in this approach.

References

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